

REVIEW ON FPGA BASED HYBRID IMAGE FUSION MODEL FOR CT AND MRI IMAGES

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Abstract

In the medical field, digital image processing is used to diagnose patients' actions linked to various disorders. Because of significant advancements in medical diagnostics tools, assessment and reflection performance has substantially increased. In medical diagnostics, two significant techniques are computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). CT has less distortion and provides better information on denser tissues, whereas MRI has greater distortion and provides the best information on soft tissues. The combination of these clinical images has opened up a new intriguing study area. According to study, the image fusion approach may capture relevant information from the many source images in fused images to provide clear images. Multimodal medical image fusion helps to acquire more information about both the functional and structural information's. To create a hybrid model, many various image fusion methods are integrated. A hybrid method is created by combining the DWT and PCA algorithms. The MSR is used to determine which DWT components have a high frequency component. The DWT method is used to efficiently transform the image's features using the average approximation fusion rule. For multimodal pictures of various organs, the image fusion approach is also used. This implementation is done on FPGA with the Xilinx Vivado environment and the Zedboard image and video processing IPs.

Key Words: CT (Computed Tomography), FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array), MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), DWT (Discrete Wavelet Transform), Principal Component Analysis, Maximum selection rule

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, image fusion (IF) is grown increasingly significant. The technique of combining two or more pictures into a single picture is known as image fusion. Two types of image fusion have been identified: transform domain and spatial domain fusion. IF has a wide range of applications, including medical, automated manufacturing, engineering, and military. Among all of these domains, the medical field application is more relevant in IF since it aids in the identification of human problems. Medical image processing is now widely used to diagnose patient activities associated with a variety of disorders. The diverse multimodalities utilized for the diagnosis of various diseases include magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), positron emission tomography (PET), computed tomography (CT), single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), and so on. The use of MRI and CT scans aids in the analysis of normal and pathological tissue as well as the interior structure of the human body. Because MRI and CT both offer information about the human brain, they are not interchangeable. Soft tissue MRI scans are used to detect skull issues, while hard tissue CT scans are utilized to assess bone structure. For a more accurate diagnosis, a combined analysis of pictures is used to obtain more information about the various organs. Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) algorithm, Non-Subsample Contour Let Transform (NSCT), sparse representation and decision, Curvelet transform, hybrid Entropy concept, hybrid Dual tree complex wavelet transform, and hybrid IF and image registration are just a few of the existing algorithms that have been used for IF. The loss of information is the main problem with these methods. The IF is being developed in FPGA to optimize efficiency and maximize hardware utilization. In FPGA, the implementation method is also unique. This study implements, hybrid algorithm PCA with DWT using maximum selection rule, to tackle the higher hardware consumption problem while utilising DWT. The MSR is solely processed by the high frequency input signal from the DWT, and the output is supplied to the Inverse DWT. The hybrid algorithm is a blend of DWT and PCA. The IF

output comes from the PCA output.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

S. Mahajan[1] Fusion techniques include the Wavelet transform (DWT), the Laplacian Pyramid Transform technique, and Principle Component Analysis (PCA). Different fused images with additional information richness were employed for the comparative analysis. Peak signal to noise ratio, mean square error, and SNR are the metrics used to evaluate performance. Using different fusion techniques, a fused image offers greater outcomes in terms of SNR and PSNR. In DWT based fused image [3],[4], The source pictures are separated into two bands, one for low associate bands and one for higher associate bands. For the function, the pixel with the most wavelet coefficients is chosen. The major benefit of using DWTs is that it will provide improved outcome (SNR). The use of the inverse discrete wavelet transform in the direction of the practised picture is the final step in the DWT- based technique. Mashetty[20] presented FPGA-based wavelet-based image fusion Spartan 3E was used to implement the proposed approach in Xilinx EDK 10.1. This FPGA contains configurable multi-national blocks for high-speed applications. Memory, flip flops, and a LUT are all part of this design. The proposed method is also used to fuse multi-focus images. The DWT does not provide stationary outputs, and the low-frequency component is inefficient. Y. Yang [21] On the basis of fuzzy logic, a multi-model based picture fusion has been proposed. NSCT was evaluated using a type 2 fuzzy with a pre-registered source image to obtain low and high bands. The local energy algorithm employs low frequency bands. With the aid of inverse NSCT and all sub bands, the proposed fused image is generated. The accuracy, contrast, and adaptability of the image were also assessed. The method's fundamental flaw is its lack of spatial resolution. The high and low bands were fused using different rules. The fused image was generated with the help of inverted NST. This method was developed using the Xilinx system generator and MATLAB. In the proposed strategy, the power value was lowered. However, this proposed solution uses a lot of hardware. V.P. Tank[11], The IF was carried out using wavelet and curvelet transforms. Curvelet transform was utilised to merge the segmented blocks into sub bands. The fused image's resolution is too low, lowering the image's quality. The hybrid approach was used to combine CT and MRI images. To accomplish the IDWT, the merged low and high level bands have been reconstructed. This hybrid approach analyses the hardware use while failing to use all the logic functions.

Image fusion is an important approach for extracting more information from multiple photos by combining different algorithms to create a hybrid fused image. There are some algorithms discussed below.

A. Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

The PCA is a computational method that may be used to convert a set of correlated variables into a set of uncorrelated variables. A new set of orthogonal axes will be generated by PCA. The direction with the greatest variation is assumed to be the first main component. The second principle component must lie in the subspace parallel to the previous principal component, and so on. [7],[16] The approach allows the spatial elements of the panchromatic picture to be included into the multispectral image by substituting the spatial component of the multispectral image with the panchromatic image.

B. Discrete Wavelet Transform

Wavelet conversions split a message into two parts: a comprehensive component and an approximate part, both of which are receiving a lot of attention. The ability to choose the degree of decomposition is the most significant benefit. Essentially, this is a multi - resolution study of brain MR images at various scales employing three-dimensional resolution. [2],[6] The discrete wavelet transformation (DWT) will also include frequency and position information. For two different resolutions, the image is divided into four parts: LH1, LL1, HL1, HH1. The quantities of estimation are the three portions of sub bands LL1, HL1, and HH1, and the element of LL1 is termed precise

index. The estimation ratio takes into account the peak data samples and can be utilized to further divide the image in LL1. Figure 2 The subbands are formed again from LL1 as LL2 (ratio of estimation), and the comprehensive values are HL2, LH2, and HH2. figure displays the double-level picture regression utilising wavelet, where the comprehensive values are HL2, LH2, and HH2. The LL2 subband can be used to further breakdown the message in the same way that tier one decay occurs. Because it contains the greatest values in all phases of decomposition, the LL subband is referred to as the crude point coefficient. At all subband concentrations, the converted indices are useful for colour assessment and differentiation. The images texture is depicted clearly by the numbers collected with in pictures subband and/or respective proportions.

Figure 1: Single level data/image decomposition

Figure 2: Double level data/image decomposition

C. Empirical mode decomposition

The versatility of empirical mode decomposition is well noted. Every aspect of the information was captured. [27].It is used to perform analysis on two-dimensional photographs. Sifting is used by EMD. After decomposition, this EMD yields Intrinsic mode functions (IMF) and a surplus item.[28]. Frequency components are intrinsic mode functions. The series of steps involved in EMD. The sites of extrema are first determined. To obtain the lower and upper envelope, the cubic spline approach is used to connect all of the maxima or minima points. The mean of both the envelopes is determined in the next step [29]. The input is deducted from the mean of the envelopes. If the generated value satisfies the IMF's standards, it will be MF1. If not, the resultant value is used as input, and the method is repeated until the result meets the IMF's requirements. The values of all zero crossings including extrema must be the same or differ with one value. All of the information from different frequencies in the original image is maintained using this method.

D. Maximum Selection rule

The pixel selection, addition, subtraction, and averaging operations are all performed via the image fusion method. Simple Average: It is true that the pixel intensity in the focused portions of the photos is higher. As a result, this method offers a simple way to produce an output image with all in-focus regions. Each image's pixel value is added together. Its average value is obtained by dividing this sum by two. The average value is assigned to the pixel in the output image that corresponds to it. It is done in the same way for all pixel values.

[25] Maximum select: For more focused portions of the image, the pixels have higher values. This rule picks the in-focus portions from each input image by selecting the larger value for each pixel, resulting in a well focused output. As a result, the pixel values of each image are taken and compared. The corresponding pixel is given to the pixel with the higher value. Researchers picked an average among detail coefficients for the both decomposed images in our Image fusion so that low frequency information (approximate information) is maintained while high frequency info (detail information) is not.

E. Image fusion by HPF

In terms of frequency band fidelity of real colour composite representation, the PCA approach generates poor results. Methods based on injecting high spatial features extracted from the panchromatic image have been introduced to definitively remove this difficulty, and have showed

3. IMPLEMENTATION RESOURCE:FIELD PROGRAMMABLE GATE ARRAY (FPGA)

FPGA allows users or developers to create logic circuits that can be altered in real time. This technology can enable hundreds of individual logic sets, as well as a large number of entry output switches and linkages, all of which can be employed based on the logic given. The image processing approach centred on extracted characteristics was introduced in this work using the Zynq Evaluation and Advanced Board (ZedBoard). The FPGA board will be programmed using Xilinx ISE/Vivado HLS. The Xilinx ISE uses intellectual property (IP) as section models and creates chip code for integrated designs as a result. It has all of the necessary characteristics and may be customized to the device of choice by allowing the building of bespoke computer logic. Because of its expandability, the board is ideal for rapid prototyping and proof-of-concept development. For image processing tasks, the software can be written in C, C++, or OpenCV. The advantages of implementing wavelet conversion on FPGA include real-time reconfigurability, simultaneous handling, and execution speeds that are comparable to those attained in software implementation.

CONCLUSION

In order to reduce hardware use, hybrid image fusion is particularly effective. Medical scans like MRI and CT have been employed in the process of fusion to get more information in this study. In comparison to earlier studies, the hybrid VLSI design gives a superior fused image. This will assist clinicians in taking the right decisions for giving more therapy using simpler and smaller independent technology. Verilog code is used to implement this. The power and area requirements were reduced using a hybrid fusion approach. For various architectures, the performance of ASICs and FPGAs can be examined.

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